

THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE ENGLISH TOURISTIC TERMINOLOGY

Khudoyberdiyeva Oydin Ismoil kizi

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Annotation: This article due to the history of the touristic terminology and also structural analysis of the English touristic terminology. Existing tourism terms in the Uzbek language Creation of annotated, electronic and translation dictionaries in Uzbek one of the important tasks of terminology.

Key words: tourism, terminology, ecotourism, business tourism.

As time progresses, it is a different field for people the doors are opening, which also has an impact on linguistics will not go unnoticed, of course. Terminology of linguistics tourism terminology, which is relatively new in the field is also expanding with new terms of this field. The development of domestic economic structures improvement, however, with this area depending on the field of activity also has a positive effect on the development of but travel make, rest in a place other than permanent residence, new see areas or health in healing areas It is also a mystery that large sums of money will be required for reconstruction it's not. These funds are used to get to the desired destination, overnight stay and accommodation, meals and so on spent for the use of services. Social The sections of the population in need of protection are partly the social of the state it is advisable to use a protection policy. In developed countries, it is specific to these population groups travel management systems have been introduced and through them Tourism services are poorly provided layers. The tourism industry also existed during the Timurid period was this was done by caravanserais built in those days and we can conclude through trips made on camels. We can be sure that it was in the time of the Timurids special attention is paid. That is the first in Movarounnahr tourist trips Amir Temur and his descendants flourished even more in his time. Tourism is legalized by tourism organizations is an area of practice that is divided into several different types divided into: domestic tourism, international tourism, amateur tourism, business tourism, ecotourism, sports tourism, auto tourism, knowledge tourism and others.

As we study tourism terminology, its attention is also paid to important aspects in the field of translation we need to focus. Used in tourism texts analyze the terms and divide them into the following groups of terms separated. For example: Emergence of new types of tourism the reason for the introduction of new terms in linguistics is happening. One of them is business tourism. Current Business in the most widely used explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language (English business, training) income-generating, any organization for profit purposes, economic activity; meanings of business explained.

Analysis of the relevant literature. Of J. Javliyeva" Analysis of the scientific literature on terminology "The article is entitled: Terminology one of the current trends in modern linguistic research is one. Terminology is on the rise on the one hand, due to the dynamic development of science due to the proliferation of new concepts, on the other hand, the process of formation of terms, adequate issues such as development and function interpreted as an unexplored phenomenon. Terminology is a very large part of the vocabulary of any language forms. Its rapid development is not in vain, because it allows you to create new words. Of a language terminology consists of a system of many terms. In a particular field of knowledge, industry or culture a word or phrase is called a term. The term expression the meaning of a word in a literature on the subject interpreted by interpretation. A word is a

linguistic term could be considered as Z. Harris wrote and I.F. Frisys. They are proponents of descriptive linguistics, word expression is defined as: "Word expression any speech of a person, whether it is before silence or then it can be expressed." Every branch of science or the school is special in its nature and methods develops terminology. Such special terminology is an important part of scientific research and is very important important. Because it contributes a lot to development Research methodology. For each industry tourism as there is a specific terminology is also large in the Uzbek terminological system takes place. Linguistic in its enrichment and extralinguistic factors are distinguished. In the last century to various fields. While the terms related to Uzbek were acquired from European languages through Russian, today they are directly foreign languages.

Applies to all types of tourism. They are representatives of this species Widely used by:

Guide, event organizer - event organizer,
chef - cook,
travel agent -travel agent,
kitchen assistan tairport baggage handler - airport cargo carrier,
tourist in formation center assistant - tourist information center delivery assistant,
sports therapist - sports specialist,
resort representative,
air traffic controller movement controller,
excursion (excursion (travel),
itinerary - direction,
overnight - during the day,
local venue -local residence (sight),
sightseeing – attraction sightseeing,
city guide - departure,
departure point - meeting point,
meeting point,
driver-guide - a guide for drivers.

Flight The route of a vehicle, such as a ship, plane, or car, on a specific route.

Flotel Floating Hotel Ship. There will be a large hotel on the water, specially equipped. Convenient,in addition to the rooms, there is a convenience for a good rest, the use of a temporary office,operative means of communication: telephone, copier, fax and other services.

Rotel Mobile hotel, with a single or double room in the form of a wagon,hotel with dressing room, common dining, common toilet.

Booking One of the hotel rooms for a specific tourist, vehicle, cultural view to book a ticket in advance.

Voucher Fees for basic services (hotel accommodation, meals, transportation, etc.)Proof of payment.

Transit Passenger from one zone to another through the third zone for no more than 24 hours,transportation of goods, etc. This term is another in the form of a compound, such as transit cargo, transit passenger also involved in the formation of terms.

In the example above, enter the foreign language into Uzbek words related to business tourism and their meanings mentioned. These terms are broad in everyday activities The

meaning is clear to everyone because it is used. Business all organizations and enterprises operating in the field. These terms are the basis for their work. As we said at the beginning, tourism all species have unique terms. Of tourism One of the larger species is ecotourism. This terms introduced into Uzbek in the field of tourism a lot. Ecotourism without harming the natural environment or is to feel nature without disturbing the population. Ecotourism in places clean in all respects, rich in unique artifacts natural tourism. This tourism through the economic condition of the indigenous people living improvement is also envisaged. M. Q. Pardayev in the article "Types of eco-tourism." thinks about the signs and purpose of ecotourism: "This There are all kinds of tourism in our country. One of them is eco-tourism. Eco-tourism is right it is necessary to identify its types in order to understand. Ecotourism, like any other type of tourism, is diverse is divided. Its different signs to explore It is worthwhile to consider the classification of there are different views on this as well. Different in this area can be approached from the perspective of. For example, tourism in the interests of investors who have provided services. According to the age and profession of tourists, ecotourism is organized to continue the same signs as for the purposes of possible. Due to this, the characters shown in this picture should be taken as an ethological basis. To each of them to understand each direction correctly requires a brief explanation. These types of ecotourism are conditional. We are divided into four groups:

- scientific tourism;
- tourism of cultural and social values;
- adventure tourism;
- nature tourism "

Ecotourism has the following characteristics of tourism means forms:

1. The main motivation of tourists is to observe nature and all nature-based tourism that is valued species, as well as traditional, distributed in natural areas cultures.
2. Educational and interpretive features in it there is.
3. It is negative to the natural and socio-cultural environment ecminimizes the effects.
4. It as an attraction of ecotourism supports the conservation of used natural areas:
 - Natural for conservation purposes host communities, organizations and economic benefits for the government;
 - Alternative work and income for local communities providing access;
 - Natural and among locals and tourists raising awareness on the preservation of cultural heritage.

As can be seen from the above, in the Uzbek language Tourism terminology is in the process of formation. As a result of the development of its composition with new special units is getting richer. Tourism is primarily the result of economic activity. This is as its homeland as it originated in England territory is recognized. Also international tourism that English is at the forefront of terminology. The main part of the Uzbek language. It is natural that he learned this language, of course. Two languages, English and Uzbek, are one area of tourism. In terms of terminology, in Uzbek some terms in their own right, some alternatives. We have witnessed the use of the option. In English many terms are given in English. But even in this language. We can find words from other languages.

Conclusion: In conclusion existing tourism terms in the Uzbek language Creation of annotated, electronic and translation dictionaries in Uzbek one of the important tasks of

terminology. Explanatory dictionaries, special for tourist terms. Giving and interpretation of terms in dictionaries with the most necessary and general insights into the subject to get acquainted and increase his level of knowledge, henceforth. It also serves to arouse interest in the field.

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